

THEORETICAL PREREQUISITES FOR THE USE OF A SCREW WORKING BODY

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After working the fields with leveling machines, the standard deviation of the heights of the roughness of the field surface is required not to exceed \pm cm every 5 m. In a layer of 0-10 cm, the amount of soil fractions smaller than 25 mm in size should not be less than 80 %.

Land leveling works in Bukhara, Navoi and Khorezm regions are carried out mainly after saline leaching and pre-sowing tillage. The main reason for this is that large roughness occurs on the surface of the field because of settling of the soil after saline washing. Therefore, leveling work is carried out after saline washing. This process should be carried out in a very short agronomic period, as it is necessary to avoid loss of soil moisture when sowing seeds in early spring and when sowing wheat in autumn. Severe soil conditions in the fields after plowing, i.e. the formation of large lumps, complicate the subsequent tillage of the soil and require the passage of agricultural machinery 2-3 times across the field. This leads to an increase in energy resources and fuel consumption [1; pp. 100-102].

Based on the review of the literature carried out, we [2; pp. 266-267] were recommended to equip the leveling bucket with an auger work member to ensure that the quality of soil compaction in the field leveling is at the level of agrotechnical requirements (Fig. 1). The auger is mounted inside the bucket and the two augers rotating in opposite directions are mounted at a certain distance from each other in the vertical and horizontal directions. Because of its application, the roughness in front of the leveling bucket is leveled and the soil mass is evenly distributed along the width of the bucket.

The process of technological operation of a leveler equipped with an auger working body is as follows: the soil collected in the bucket of the leveler is pushed in a transverse direction using augers. In this case, the augers push the soil in different directions: one auger pushes the soil to the left of the bucket, and the other pushes it to the opposite side, i.e. to the right. As a result, the soil is evenly distributed over the coverage width of the bucket and has a positive effect on the level and quality of leveling of the plot. The rotation of the soil with the augers and the impact of the cut stalks and large pieces on each other

ensures their crushing, improving the structural composition of the soil surface layer before planting and the formation of a soft layer.

The parameters that affect the performance of a leveler equipped with an auger working body are the follow (Fig. 1):

- type of auger;
- auger diameter D_u ;
- auger step l_u ;
- auger rotation speed n_u ;
- auger length L_u ;
- longitudinal distance between the leveling bucket and the auger L ;
- longitudinal distance between augers L_δ ;
- vertical distance between the augers L_T ;
- movement speed of the unit V_u .

Fig. 1. Parameters of auger work member